

D4.1 Interim report of the results from WP4

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

Bio-based systems (BbS)
Work Package (WP)
Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)
Life Cycle Inventory (LCI)
Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA)
Environmental Life Cycle Costing (eLCC)
Social Hotspots Database (SHDB)
EU Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (CSDDD).
Job Creation Potential (JCP)
Occupational Health and Safety (OHS)
Occupational Exposure Limits (OELs)
Product Environmental Footprint (PEF)

PROJECT INFORMATION

Project full title: Harmonised Life Cycle Assessment methods for sustainable and circular BIO based systems

Acronym: LCA4BIO

Call: HORIZON-CL6-2023-ZEROPOLLUTION-01

Topic: HORIZON-CL6-2023-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-04 - Environmental sustainability and circularity criteria for industrial bio-based systems

Start date: 1st January 2024

Duration: 36 months

List of participants:

PARTNER N°	PARTICIPANT ORGANIZATION	ACRONYM
1 (Coord.)	CONTACTICA SL	CTA
2	AALBORG UNIVERSITET	AAU
3	LUXEMBOURG INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY	LIST
4	INSTITUT NATIONAL DES SCIENCES APPLIQUEES DE TOULOUSE	INSA
5	NORGES TEKNISK-NATURVITENSKAPELIGE UNIVERSITET	NTNU
6	BIOECONOMY FOR CHANGE	B4C
7	BUSINESS E-INCUBATOR GO-UP	GOUP
8	FUNDACION CENTRO DE SERVICIOS Y PROMOCION FORESTAL Y DE SU INDUSTRIA DE CASTILLA Y LEON	CESEFOR
9	SONAE ARAUCO PORTUGAL SA	SONAE
10	ASOCIACION PARA LA CERTIFICACION ESPANOLA FORESTAL	PEFC

DELIVERABLE DETAILS

Document Number:	D4.1
Document Title:	Interim report of the results from WP4
Dissemination level	PU – Public, fully open,
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Task:	T4.1, T4.2, T4.3
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Abstract:	WP4 intends to analyse some of the limits in the widespread production and use of biobased products, by investigating issues of competition for biomass resources and of substitutability between fossil and biobased products. The current report documents the interim results across three tasks: the analysis of substitution effects via review and survey efforts; the analysis of trade-offs and synergies via review of tools for life cycle costing and social LCA; and the analysis of competition with adjacent economy sectors in the bioeconomy via the creation of a model of biomass flows in Europe at present and in the future. The report includes a brief description of the work done in the first project reporting period as well as preliminary results and information on the next steps.

Version	Date	Description
1.0	2025-06-25	First version
2.0	2025-06-26	Second draft for review
3.0	2025-06-27	Final version

1 OVERALL OBJECTIVE OF WP4

WP4 sets to investigate the trade-offs and synergies caused by the growth of bio-based systems (BbS). Specifically, WP4 has three objectives:

- O4.1. To analyse the substitution effect methodologies for bio-based products.
- O4.2. To analyse trade-offs and synergies between improved environmental performance and economic and social objectives of BbS.
- O4.3. To analyse trade-offs and synergies with competing and adjacent economy sectors in the bioeconomy.

The objectives are addressed in three corresponding tasks:

- **Task 4.1 (AAU lead)** *Definition and analysis of methodologies for substitution effects of BbS (M6-M30)* [AAU,CTA,LIST,INSA,NTNU,GOUP,CESEFOR]
- **Task 4.2 (CTA lead)** *Methods to assess socio-economic trade-offs and synergies of BbS (M6-M30)* [CTA, AAU, GOUP]
- **Task 4.3 (AAU lead)** *Accounting for competition for resources between BbS with energy, food and feed sectors (M6-M30)* [AAU, LIST, NTNU]

In the following sections, the interim and preliminary results obtained in the period M6-M18 for each task are presented.

2 INTERIM AND PRELIMINARY RESULTS

2.1 Task 4.1 Interim and preliminary results on definition and analysis of methodologies for substitution effects of BbS.

2.1.1 Objective of T4.1

The main objective of this task was to review and analyse the challenges encountered when substituting and replacing fossil-based products with bio-based alternatives. While most of the existing literature focuses on the benefits of this substitution, it often overlooks the associated challenges and differences in performance. Moreover, the few studies that address such challenges adopt a specific product focus rather than considering a class of similar products or a sector. This task, therefore, focused on addressing this gap by analysing the challenges from a broader perspective across multiple sectors. In this way, it provides a more comprehensive understanding of the barriers.

2.1.2 Review and survey on substitution effects

The task included a review and a survey.

The review included five sectors: construction, packaging, textiles, chemicals, and woodworking. The analysis consisted of two main parts: compiling a list of challenges associated with substitution and assessing whether these challenges were addressed in the selected comparative LCA (Life Cycle Assessment) studies. Several articles were selected based on the abstract, publication year, and citation counts. First the Google Scholar database was used for the search, after the number of studies was extended using the AI-based tool Research Rabbit. In total, 44 scientific papers were reviewed to identify challenges. Once challenges were listed based on the review of the selected papers, a summary was made of whether the challenges were addressed in the selected comparative LCA studies. To find relevant comparative LCA studies, the same search approach was used. The goal was to have four to five comparative LCA studies per sector. In total, 23 comparative studies were analysed. Preliminary findings from the review were then used to inform the survey.

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The survey study, titled "Bio-based Companies and Their Development in Europe" was initiated to identify and analyze the challenges hindering the growth of bio-based industries and businesses within the European Union. The survey was designed to collect detailed information from key stakeholders in the bio-based sector. The questionnaire was distributed to a diverse, representative shortlist of stakeholders from the biobased value chain suggested by Go-Up and complemented by partners. The distribution was undergone via email, followed by phone calls to encourage participation. Despite these efforts, gathering a good number of respondents proved to be a significant challenge, with a total of only 15 responses received: 53.3% from Bulgaria and 46.7% from other European countries. These participants hailed from various nations, including Bulgaria, Greece, and Portugal, and represented diverse sectors such as the food and beverage industry, construction, textile industry, and renewable energy production.

2.1.3 Preliminary findings

Regarding the findings of the review, an exemplary case is provided in the following. One of the identified challenges in substituting fossil-based products with bio-based alternatives in the construction sector is fire resistance. For example, to ensure fire resistance in a wooden construction one needs to use additional gypsum board. Therefore, as a next step, it was investigated whether the five retrieved comparative LCS studies that focused on the use of biobased products in the construction sector, in this case wood structures, addressed the difference in fire resistance in the LCA. It was found that four out of the five analysed studies did address this challenge. Challenges in the other sectors were investigated in the same way. One of the findings was that challenges such as material properties, biodegradability, and differences in technical processing were mostly addressed in the analysed LCA studies. However, most studies have overlooked challenges like the need for coatings or additional treatments and differences in environmental durability. In the end, key recommendations by each life cycle phase were provided (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Recommendations for LCA practitioners based on the findings from the review of challenges in substituting fossil products with biobased ones.

The interim survey results indicate that the primary motivations for starting a bio-based business are predominantly environmental (33.3%), economic (20%), and social (20%). Among respondents, 29.5% cited *Economic challenges* (high investment costs, price competition), 20.5% encountered *Market challenges* (lack of consumer knowledge, supply chain, etc.), and 15.9% faced *Social challenges* (lack of awareness, non-acceptance of new products, fear of losing jobs). Some specific challenges shared by respondents include:

"Suppliers of raw materials not always capable or willing to supply. Additionally, in assessments, it is not always clear what aspects to incorporate or not."

"Lack of data from the suppliers regarding the sustainability performance, namely CO2 emissions impact."

"It's all a matter of time and an additional task for us. But we think it's very important to have such a report done by an independent and licensed company."

Respondents also emphasized the need for collaboration and support from various stakeholders:

"It is very important to talk about the importance of this step - to move from non-organic options to renewable and compostable packaging. Of course, we have a major role as a business, but we also need support from scientists, the media and all stakeholders to have an opinion and share their experiences."

2.1.4 Status and future plans

Regarding the review, work is currently in process on writing a scientific paper that provides a detailed analysis of the challenges associated with the substitution of fossil-based products with bio-based alternatives across the five sectors. The paper will also contain recommendations for LCA practitioners conducting comparative LCA studies of bio-based and fossil-based products.

Regarding the survey, an issue was to find a sufficiently high number of respondents to allow for statistical analysis of the results and to have diversity across them to generalize conclusions. Despite many attempts to circulate the survey in the LCA4BIO project's stakeholder networks it seems that obtaining high response numbers is unrealistic. To overcome this challenge of the survey and gain a more comprehensive understanding of the problem, it was decided to conduct in-depth interviews with the existing survey respondents. This approach will allow to gather more detailed information about the specific needs, challenges, and motivations driving organizations in the bio-based industries. By delving deeper into their experiences, the aim is to uncover richer, more nuanced insights that were not possible through the survey alone. The plan is to start with interviews among key people among the existing survey respondents, who have provided more elaborate responses or are willing to engage in a detailed discussion, and then after several iterations of the interview questions and methodology, move on to interview all other survey respondents.

2.2 Task 4.2 interim and preliminary results on methods to assess socio-economic trade-offs and synergies of BbS

2.2.1 Objective of Task 4.2

The main objective of this task is to analyse socio-economic trade-offs and synergies between Bio-based Systems (BbS). To that end, a review of key socio-economic objectives for the EU, social and economic indicators in the literature, and the work carried out in other EU funded projects such as CALIMERO, ALIGNED and ORIENTED was performed, to cover the need to add more comprehensive socio-economic indicators into LCSA for BbS. In that sense, it is ensured that the full range of sustainability impacts are considered, allowing us at the same time to assess socio-economic trade-offs, synergies, and substitution effects more effectively.

2.2.2 Review of EU key socio-economic objectives

First, a review of EU objectives, policies, and strategies was carried out. EU prioritizes sustainability through strategies like the Bioeconomy Strategy, the European Green Deal, and the Social Economy Action Plan, all of them aligned with the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), adopted by all UN Member States in 2015. The findings of this review of socio-economic objectives for the EU conclude that the strategic objectives of the SDGs and Sustainable Energy Action Plan (SEAP) coincide with the development of the European Union's bioeconomy strategy, which focuses on 5 main areas: ensuring food and nutrition security, sustainable management of natural resources, reducing dependence on non-renewable sources, reducing the negative

impact on nature and adapting to climate change, strengthening European competitiveness and creating jobs. These challenges lead to new strategic decisions, with new insights on innovation being identified in several European countries related to resource efficiency, improved solutions and services in reducing environmental impacts as well as enhancing life cycle and sustainable innovation process development (Zaimova & Gospodinova, 2023).

In summary, a sustainable bioeconomy based on EU strategies, can play a pivotal role by:

- Economically: boosting GDP, job creation, and innovation.
- Socially: reducing inequality, improving infrastructure, and promoting education.

2.2.3 Review of current approaches in social analysis

After having a clear idea of EU objectives, a review of the literature and ongoing EU-funded projects was conducted to identify relevant indicators for assessing social impacts and substitution effects in bioeconomy. In literature, recent reviews (Rafiaani et al., Siebert et al., Marting Vidaurre et al., Rebolledo-Leiva et al., Zarauz et al.) have compiled and analysed social indicators relevant to biobased systems. Commonly assessed aspects include health and safety, income, local employment, food and energy security, gender issues, and labour rights. Regional choices of indicators were also observed, such as child and forced labour in Latin America and job creation in Europe and North America. These insights underscore the importance of context-driven, empirically grounded indicators for effective social impact assessment in bioeconomy-related value chains.

Referring to other EU-funded projects, the Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) methodology developed in ORIENTING applies a five-level Reference Scale approach to assess social performance and risk. This method combines qualitative and quantitative evaluations, scoring impacts from +2 (positive) to -2 (negative) across 29 social topics. Risk is assessed using the Social Hotspots Database (SHDB), while social performance is measured using primary data from companies, such as internal documents and websites. Some limitations identified include difficulties obtaining upstream/downstream data, dependency on Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) inventories, a lack of clarity in scoring scales, risks of misinterpretation when combining social topics, and limited alignment with regulatory frameworks like the EU Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (CSDDD).

The CALIMERO project complements ORIENTING by focusing on sustainability in bio-based sectors. It identifies methodological and conceptual gaps in socio-economic assessments, such as the lack of bioeconomy-specific indicators, limited focus beyond production phases, and weak alignment with bioeconomy job creation strategies. In that sense, CALIMERO refines the Job Creation Potential (JCP) indicator, which estimates the number of jobs generated by a product system, distinguishing between direct and indirect jobs, worker levels, and gender. However, it warns that job creation in one sector can result in job losses in another, an aspect that is often overlooked and necessary to assess substitution effects in the bioeconomy. In addition, CALIMERO proposes new indicators for Occupational Health and Safety (OHS), such as Occupational Exposure Limits (OELs), and explores the use of AI and machine learning to improve toxicity assessments, addressing social aspects currently missing in the Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) method. The project also reviewed key S-LCA standards and databases, such as UNEP guidelines, ISO standards, Ecovadis, Sedex, and PSILCA. Among the assessment methods, the Reference Scale approach is seen as more applicable than the Impact Pathway method, although both face challenges like inconsistent terminology, unclear frameworks, and limited recognition of positive impacts.

2.2.4 Review of current approaches in economic analysis

In terms of economic assessment in BbS, it was found in the literature that several studies have explored eLCC using different methodologies and tools. The value-added approach (e.g., Heijungs et al., 2013) evaluates life cycle costs based on the difference between revenue and production cost, though some models required revisions to ensure realistic assumptions (e.g., avoiding negative value-added). Although many studies apply

eLCC, integrating it with LCA can be complex due to potential double counting of environmental impacts. Some researchers apply eLCC and LCA in parallel with consistent boundaries (e.g., Ferrara et al., 2023), while others limit the scope of eLCC to avoid data uncertainties or double counting (e.g., Faraca et al., 2019; Chiesa et al., 2016). Some assessments don't follow standardized frameworks but still offer useful insights. New approaches are being developed for more integrated analysis, such as: The Unit Cost Model, that enables assessment of all three LCC types; or the DEALA method that evaluates economic impacts in complex systems, such as battery supply chains, and can support both eLCC and broader sustainability assessments.

A review of economic analysis was carried out on three key EU-funded projects: ALIGNED, CALIMERO, and ORIENTING. ALIGNED developed a Techno-Economic Assessment (TEA) tool in Excel, allowing users to input operational and financial data and calculate economic indicators such as Net Present Value (NPV), Internal Rate of Return (IRR), Discounted Payback Period (DPBP), and Levelized Cost of Product (LCP). CALIMERO adopted an environmental Life Cycle Costing (eLCC) approach that includes both internal and selected external costs, while avoiding monetization of social and environmental impacts to prevent double counting in LCSA. It provides an Excel-based calculator to compute indicators like LCC, NPV, LCOP, IRR, Payback Period (PP), and Environmental Externalities. Like ALIGNED, the focus is on industrial manufacturing stages. ORIENTING developed a method that includes all life cycle costs and positive cash flows, accounting for externalities like GHG emissions and employment, avoiding double counting. It distinguishes between three stakeholder groups: consumers, producers, and society, ensuring data compatibility by converting all inputs to a common functional unit. These projects provide valuable frameworks and tools for LCSA, though they tend to emphasize manufacturing stages, often overlooking other key phases in BbS such as end-of-life, not allowing for a proper assessment of substitution effects in the bioeconomy.

2.2.5 Ongoing work and next steps

After the deep review that is being summarized in this report, a comparative analysis of key indicators is currently being performed to identify the most suitable methods for measuring trade-offs, synergies and socio-economic substitution effects, supporting informed decision-making and policy development. The indicator selection criteria focuses on their ability to measure trade-offs and synergies across dimensions such as employment, income distribution, resource efficiency, and market competitiveness, linking them to the SDGs targets.

2.3 **Task 4.3 interim and preliminary results on accounting for competition for resources between BbS with energy, food and feed sectors**

2.3.1 Objective of T4.3

The main objective of this task is to develop an operational framework and guidance to account for the constraints of and competition for biomass in the LCA of emerging bio-based technologies. This is currently not common practice in LCA (Talwar and Holden, 2022). Moreover, conventional LCA methodologies do not allow for considering limitations (present and future) of biomass feedstocks.

This task, so far, has focused on developing a framework to identify constrained biomass feedstocks, bioeconomy sectors competing for the same feedstocks, and non-bioeconomy sectors that will respond to deficits – lack of available supply – in biomass. Using this framework enables the modelling of new demand for biomass under current and future, projected bioeconomy scenarios, and quantifies of the resulting deficits in competing sectors. The scope of this work is focused on the EU.

The following sections will provide details about the framework: the EU Biomass Matrix, the optimization script used for modelling new demand for biomass, and the future bioeconomy projections. Additionally, a case study

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for applying the framework in the LCA of a bio-based product is presented, alongside with the plans for further development of the framework in Task 4.3.

2.3.2 The EU Biomass Matrix

Data sources

The Joint Research Centre of the European Commission (JRC) has been collecting data and providing analysis on biomass supply and demand in both the EU and globally under the JRC Biomass Mandate. As a part of this effort, several comprehensive, retrospective accounts of EU biomass stocks and flows have been published. The latest of these published datasets has been used as a basis for our calculations, the matrix, and the future projections (Avitabile et al., 2023). The dataset allows to map the flows of biomass from primary sources (e.g., forestry, fishery, and agriculture) through processing sectors, down to finished products, all expressed in a single unit, i.e., kt of dry biomass. While the JRC provides a great overall account of the EU Bioeconomy, some of the biomass flows lack resolution, and many currently underutilized resources are omitted. Hence, it must be complemented with other sources as we develop the framework further, for example with scientific literature published about the availability of residue-streams.

Constructing the matrix and the optimization script

The JRC biomass flow dataset was transformed into a matrix format where feedstock production is linked to intermediate and final utilization and demand. The structure of this EU Biomass Matrix is like that of a conventional matrix-form life cycle inventory (LCI). This matrix represents the current state of the bioeconomy – which then serves as a basis framework for further calculations. When performing prospective analyses, this start matrix is modified to reflect changes in the state of the bioeconomy under the desired timeframe and developmental pathway. For example, the availability of primary sources of biomass and demand for each bioeconomy sector in the year 2050 under an “Middle of the Road” global climate change scenario, together with the assumption that the EU will pursue an ambitious transition to a sustainable bioeconomy, can be used to obtain an updated version of the matrix describing the bioeconomy under these premises.

The next step in the framework is investigating the consequences of introducing a new bio-based product to the market, which in turn means introducing new demand for biomass feedstocks to the market. An optimization script was developed in python 3.13 using the PuLP 3.1.1. package. The model allows the user to specify the constraints of the bioeconomy, for example to allow certain feedstock flows to respond to growing demand while forcing others to remain fully utilized. Additionally, the user can define new demand for a specific biomass sector or feedstock. The optimization model then, taking into consideration the constraints and obligatory ratios between feedstocks and residues or products and by-products, re-distributes the available biomass to fulfil the new demand. In case of shortage of biomass, the model identifies the potential sectors where a deficit of feedstock will occur and provides the quantity of the deficit. The deficit is equally spread across the competing sectors that rely on the same flow where the shortage occurred. These results are reported both as individual datapoints, and as a new, result matrix with the new demand and the deficits incorporated, the latter resulting from a lower demand compared to the unoptimized matrix. These results enable the user to (1) identify the trade-offs of introducing new demand for a specific feedstock, (2) evaluate the impacts of the resulting deficit, and (3) construct the marginal mix for their consequential LCA model.

2.3.3 EU Bioeconomy Futures

Data sources

The JRC-data used for constructing the EU Biomass Matrix is historical. Hence, it must be complemented with other sources to create future scenarios for prospective assessments for emerging technologies. Data for future projections or visions of the EU bioeconomy can be obtained from several sources, including policy target documents, sector-specific accounts and projections, climate models, expert panels and reports, and scientific literature. So far the following sources have been used: the Shared Socio-Economic Pathways (SSPs),

the “Foresight scenarios for the EU bioeconomy in 2050” by the EC’s Knowledge Center for Bioeconomy (Fritsche et al., 2021), the “Integrated assessment of bioeconomy sustainability” report by the JRC, and a report on simulating future wood consumption in the EU also by the JRC (Rougieux et al., 2024).

Modified start matrix

In the developed framework, the start matrix reflects the expected supply and demand in a chosen scenario. The objective of the Task is to pre-define scenarios to allow for the comparison between the environmental performance of a novel bio-based technology under different assumptions. These could be for example a more- and less optimistic scenarios for global climate change, different policy landscapes governing the EU bioeconomy transitions, and trends in the production yields and processing capacities of biomass in the EU.

In the first phase of this Task, a scenario was created in which with only the forestry-related sectors of the EU Bioeconomy projected into 2050 under the SSP2 and an assumption of increased harvesting of logging residues in European forests.

2.3.4 Applying the framework on a case study

Comparing results: LCA with and without the integration of biomass constraints

The framework was applied in a case study to test the concept and the optimization on empirical data (Figure 2). A published LCA study (Aryapratama & Janssen, 2017) of a bio-based chemical made from forestry residues was chosen; because of the detailed documentation of the LCA modelling and the relatively low complexity of the biomass value chain involved. The original study did not include any modelling of biomass constraints.

Two scenarios were compared. In both, the future market demand for the target chemical was assumed to be satisfied entirely by the bio-based alternative. In the first scenario, only the environmental burdens and savings calculated in the original study were included. In the second, additional burdens due to the constraints of the feedstock and the resulting substitution were also included, calculated with the EU Biomass Matrix. The final LCA results of producing the amount of the target chemical that is expected by industry projections to cover the entire European demand were then compared. By testing different modelling assumptions, it was calculated that including the additional burdens due to the biomass constraints reduced the CO₂ emissions savings predicted by the original study. The size of this reduction was between a few percents and nearly half of the savings depending on the modelling assumptions. The results of this comparison are in fact highly dependent on assumptions about the future market conditions, the substitution rate between fossil and bio-based counterparts, future energy systems, and other aspects. The significant changes in the prospected life cycle impacts support the need for the further development of the framework.

Figure 2. The figure shows a segment of the bioeconomy where new demand for a novel bio-based product results in unintended demand for fossil resources. The interaction between the bio- and non-bioeconomy sectors are visualized in a simplified version of the EU Bioeconomy Matrix. Sources: [1] Avitabile et al., 2023 [2] Fritsche et al., 2021 [3] Rougieux et al., 2024

2.3.5 Ongoing work and next steps

Refining the EU Bioeconomy Matrix and the optimization script

Since the case study showed that using the EU Bioeconomy Matrix can have significant impact on the LCA of biotechnologies, the concept will be further developed by increasing the resolution of the biomass flows and modifying the optimization script to accommodate more complex case studies, both on the product- and sector-level.

Defining further comprehensive EU Bioeconomy Futures scenarios

In the next phase of the project, beyond the case-specific scenario used in the case study, more comprehensive scenarios describing the EU bioeconomy under different policy and economic landscapes, geophysical limits, and at different points of time will be defined. These scenarios will be used for modelling further biotechnologies together with a consequential LCA approach. Current work includes comparing biomass-related future scenarios in Integrated Assessment Models, the premise-generated databases (Sacchi et al., 2022), as well as other research projects and published literature.

Addressing uncertainties

As discussed above, there are high levels of uncertainty in the results of the framework. Going forward, in collaboration with other Work Packages and Tasks focusing on uncertainty analysis, further investigation of the influence of modelling choices and data quality on the results will be carried out.

3 MANAGEMENT AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

3.1 Management of WP

WP4 meetings have been held monthly lead by AAU. Agenda was sent in advance. Minutes have been taking at each meeting and shared.

3.2 Dissemination to scientific audiences

Members from LCA4BIO met during the SETAC Europe 35th Annual Meeting, Vienna, Austria, 11-15 May (Figure 3). Narie Rinke Dias de Souza (NTNU), Kíra Lancz (AAU) and Marjorie Morales (LIST) (Figure 4) co-chaired the joint LCA4BIO/ALIGNED session “Methodological Advancements in Life Cycle Assessment of Emerging Bio-Based Systems”. Results of LCA4BIO from WP4 were presented by project members in five scientific presentations at this session (Table 1).

Figure 3. Members from LCA4BIO at SETAC 2025

Figure 4 Co-chairs of the joint LCA4BIO/ALIGNED scientific session

Table 1. LCA4BIO presentations at SETAC Europe 2025

Title	Presenter	Affiliation
Challenges in Substituting Fossil Products with Bio-based Alternatives (Platform)	Ewa Katarzyna Lagodzka	AAU
Job Creation Potential Tool for Assessing Employment Opportunities in a Bio-Economy Context (Platform)	Eduardo Entrena-Barbero	CTA
Towards the Integration of Bioeconomy Constraints in Life Cycle Assessment (Poster spotlight)	Kíra Lancz	AAU
More Than Just Business: The Bioeconomy Supporting the Development of New Sustainable Business Models in Bulgaria (Poster)	Elena Gospodinova	GOUP
Life cycle assessment approaches and applications to emerging bio-based technologies (Poster)	Narie Rinke Dias de Souza	NTNU

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